

Privacy-Preserving Sequential Publishing of Knowledge Graphs

Anh-Tu Hoang
DiSTA
University of Insubria, Italy
ahoang@uninsubria.it

Barbara Carminati
DiSTA
University of Insubria, Italy
barbara.carminati@uninsubria.it

Elena Ferrari
DiSTA
University of Insubria, Italy
elena.ferrari@uninsubria.it

Abstract—Knowledge graphs (KGs) are widely shared because they can model both users’ attributes as well as their relationships. Unfortunately, adversaries can re-identify their victims in these KGs by using a rich background knowledge about not only the victims’ attributes but also their relationships. A preliminary work to deal with this issue has been proposed in [1] which anonymizes both user attributes and relationships, but this is not enough. Indeed, adversaries can still re-identify target users if data providers publish new versions of their anonymized KGs. We remedy this problem by presenting the k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree (k^w -tad) principle that prevents adversaries from re-identifying any user appearing in w continuous anonymized KGs with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$. Moreover, we introduce the Cluster-based Time-Varying Knowledge Graph Anonymization Algorithm to generate anonymized KGs satisfying k^w -tad. Finally, we prove that even if data providers insert/re-insert/update/delete their users, the users are protected by k^w -tad.

Index Terms—anonymity, privacy, dynamic knowledge graphs.

I. INTRODUCTION

More and more data providers are using Knowledge Graphs (KGs) to share their data, since KGs can describe not only users’ attributes but also their relationships. For instance, after the announcement of Google Knowledge Graph in 2012, many giant tech companies (e.g., Wikipedia, Amazon, Microsoft) have announced their developments on KGs. Although data providers remove users’ explicit identities from KGs, adversaries can still re-identify them by using both their attributes and relationships [1]. Therefore, providers must anonymize their KGs before releasing them.

There are two main anonymization approaches: k -anonymity and differential privacy (DP) [2]. k -anonymity modifies users’ data such that adversaries cannot infer users’ identities with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$ even though these adversaries exploit their background knowledge about the users. DP aims at designing an analysis algorithm to generate analytical results from a dataset without leaking users’ identity. Since we aim at publishing the anonymized KGs that can be used for many scenarios (e.g., graph analysis), we focus on k -anonymity approach in this paper.

Recently, k -AttributeDegree (k -ad) [1], an extension of k -anonymity [2], has been presented to prevent adversaries from re-identifying any user in an anonymized KG by ensuring that his/her attributes’ values and relationships’ out-/in-degrees

in the anonymized KG are indistinguishable from those of $k - 1$ other users in the KG. Therefore, even if the adversaries exploit the attributes’ values and relationships’ out-/in-degrees of their victims, they cannot re-identify the victims in the KG with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$. However, k -ad cannot protect users if data providers periodically publish new versions of the anonymized KG. The following example shows how adversaries can re-identify users in anonymized KGs satisfying k -ad.

Example 1. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 illustrate the original KGs and their 2-ad anonymized versions at time: 0, 1, 2. As \overline{G}_0 , \overline{G}_1 , and \overline{G}_2 satisfy 2-ad, adversaries cannot re-identify any user in these KGs if they gain access to only one of them. However, by associating \overline{G}_0 , \overline{G}_1 , and \overline{G}_2 , they can re-identify *user:0*, *user:1*, *user:2*, *user:3*, and *user:4*. First, if they know that *Jane* exists in \overline{G}_1 and does not exist in \overline{G}_0 , they can identify that *user:4* is *Jane*, as she is the only new user. Moreover, they can also identify that *user:0* in \overline{G}_1 is *Ken*, if they know that *Ken* has just changed his job from *Student* to *Engineer* at time 1. In addition, they can detect that *user:3* in \overline{G}_1 is *Tom*, as he is the only one who has been removed in \overline{G}_1 . Finally, they can figure out that *user:3* in \overline{G}_2 is *Tom*, as there is only one user who has been re-inserted in \overline{G}_2 .

The problem of preventing adversaries from re-identifying users by accessing different versions of an anonymized dataset has been studied in the context of undirected [3], [4] and directed [5] graphs. Tai et al. [3] proposed the k^w -SDA model to protect users from being re-identified when the adversaries monitor users’ degrees in w continuous anonymized graph snapshots, but their model allows users to have only one attribute. Macwan et al. [4] extended [3] to allow users to have many attributes. Zhang et al. [5] presented the Dynamic Social Network Directed Graph K-In&Out-Degree Anonymity Model to protect users’ identities when adversaries gain access to continuous anonymized directed graphs. However, [3]–[5] cannot protect users in anonymized KGs containing both attributes’ values and different relationship types. To the best of our knowledge, we are not aware of any proposal addressing the issue of privacy-preserving publishing of multiple releases of a KG.

To cope with this issue, we present k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree (k^w -tad), an extension of k -ad [1], to protect

Fig. 1. Different snapshots of a KG at time $t = 0, 1, 2$.

Fig. 2. 2-ad anonymized versions of G_0 , G_1 , and G_2 .

users from being re-identified even if adversaries gain access to w continuous anonymized snapshots of a KG. We extend k -ad in this work because it is the only protection model that can protect users' identities in anonymized KGs. In particular, we assume that adversaries can know attributes' values and relationships' out/in-degrees of their victims in w continuous anonymized KGs. k^w -tad protects any user appearing at least once in these KGs, by ensuring that the series of his/her attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degree in these KGs is indistinguishable from that of $k - 1$ other users who also appear at least once in these KGs. Then, the adversaries cannot re-identify the users with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$, even if they gain access to w continuous anonymized KGs.

and out-degree of *classmate_of* relationship identical to those of *user:4*, adversaries cannot identify which node is *Jane*. Moreover, as *job* of both *user:0* and *user:1* in \bar{G}_1 is *Student* or *Engineer*, adversaries cannot detect which node is *Ken*. Because *age*, *job*, and in-degree of *follows* relationship in \bar{G}_0 of *user:2* and *user:3* are identical, and both of them are removed in \bar{G}_1 , the adversaries also cannot identify which node is *Tom* in \bar{G}_1 . Furthermore, as both of them are re-inserted in \bar{G}_2 , adversaries cannot identify which node is *Tom* in \bar{G}_2 . For each user appearing at least once in \bar{G}_0 , \bar{G}_1 , and \bar{G}_2 , the series of his/her attributes' values and out-/in-degrees of relationships in these KGs is indistinguishable from that of another user who also appear in these KGs. Then, adversaries cannot re-identify any user with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{2}$.

Fig. 3. 2^3 -tad versions of G_1 and G_2 ($\bar{G}_0 = \bar{G}'_0$).

Example 2. Fig. 3 illustrates the 2^3 -tad anonymized versions of G_0 , G_1 , and G_2 presented in Fig. 1. Here \bar{G}_0 is identical to \bar{G}'_0 (Fig. 2a), as G_0 is the first version of the original KG. By adding the fake user *fake:0* to \bar{G}_1 and make its *job*

Moreover, we present the Cluster-based Time-Varying Knowledge Graph Anonymization Algorithm (CTKGA) to anonymize the current version of the original KG such that the series of the current and $w - 1$ previous anonymized KGs satisfies k^w -tad. First, the proposed algorithm generates clusters such that the series of attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees in $w - 1$ previous anonymized KGs of users who are in the same cluster is identical and all the clusters have at least k users. Also, it adds fake users to ensure that all inserted users, who exist in the current original KG but do not exist in previous anonymized KGs, are in clusters that have at least k users. Furthermore, it ensures that, for each deleted user, who exists in previous anonymized KGs and does not exist the current KG, the series of his/her attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in $w - 1$ previous anonymized KGs is indistinguishable from that of $k - 1$ other deleted users. Finally, we use the Knowledge Graph Generalization Algorithm [1], [6] to make the attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees of users who are in the same cluster identical. We prove that even if data providers update their original KG by inserting, re-inserting, and deleting users or updating edges of their users, our algorithm can anonymize the original KG

TABLE I
NOTATIONS USED IN THE PAPER.

Symbol	Meaning
G_t, \bar{G}_t	the original and anonymized KG at time t
g_t^w, \bar{g}_t^w	the series of w original and anonymized KGs from time $t - w + 1$ to t
$I_a(G_t, u)$	attributes' values of user u in G_t
$I_o(G_t, u)$	out-degrees of user u in G_t
$I_i(G_t, u)$	in-degrees of user u in G_t
$I(G_t, u)$	attributes' values and out-/in-degrees of user u in G_t
$\mathcal{I}(g_t^w, u)$	the series of $I(G_t, u)$ in anonymized KGs of g_t^w
$\mathcal{BK}_t(u)$	the background knowledge about user u at time t
$\mathcal{BK}_t^w(u)$	the series of background knowledge about user u from time $t - w + 1$ to t
$\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$	the set of users appearing at least once in \bar{g}_t^w
\mathcal{T}	the attacking mechanism to re-identify a user

such that the series of w continuous anonymized KGs always satisfies k^w -tad.

The remaining sections of this paper are organized as follows. Section II illustrates our privacy protection model. Then, Section III presents our anonymization algorithm. In Section IV, we conclude this paper.

II. IDENTITY PROTECTION IN SEQUENTIAL PUBLISHING OF KNOWLEDGE GRAPHS

As users' data change over time, a data provider may hold many versions of their data. We model each version as a distinct knowledge graph (KG). Specifically, we model a KG generated at time t as $G_t(V_t, E_t, R_t)$, where V_t is the set of nodes, E_t is the set of edges connecting these nodes, and R_t is the set of relationship types at time t . As a node in a KG illustrates either a user or an attribute' value, the set V_t contains two subsets: the set $V_t^U \subseteq V_t$, modelling users (e.g., $user:0, user:1$), and the set $V_t^A \subseteq V_t$, representing attributes' values (e.g., $18, Student$). Similarly, the set R_t contains two subsets: the set of user-to-user relationship types R_t^{UU} , representing users' relationships (e.g., $follows$), and the set of user-to-attribute relationship types R_t^{UA} , modelling users' attributes (e.g., age, job). Each edge $e \in E_t$ is defined as a triple (u, r, v) , where $u, v \in V_t$ and $r \in R_t$. We denote with $E_t^{UA} \subseteq E_t$ those $e = (u, r_a, v_a)$, such that $r_a \in R_t^{UA}$. Similarly, we denote with E_t^{UU} those $e = (u, r_u, v_u)$, such that $r_u \in R_t^{UU}$.

Let u be a user in G_t . We denote with $I_a(G_t, u) = \{(r_a, v_a) | (u, r_a, v_a) \in E_t^{UA}\}$ the values of u 's attributes in G_t . Let $d_o(G_t, r_u, u) = |\{(u, r_u, v) \in E_t^{UU}\}|$ and $d_i(G_t, r_u, u) = |\{(v, r_u, u) \in E_t^{UU}\}|$ be the out- and in-degree of relationship type $r_u \in R_t^{UU}$ of u . We denote with $I_o(G_t, u) = \{(r_u, d_o(G_t, r_u, u)) | r_u \in R_t^{UU}\}$, and $I_i(G_t, u) = \{(r_u, d_i(G_t, r_u, u)) | r_u \in R_t^{UU}\}$ the out- and in-degrees of u in G_t , respectively. Then, we denote with $I(G_t, u) = (I_a(G_t, u), I_o(G_t, u), I_i(G_t, u))$ the information of u in G_t .

Table I summarizes the main notations used in the paper.

A. Adversary Background Knowledge

At each publication time t , a data provider releases a KG G_t that evolves from G_{t-1} by adding/removing some of its edges/nodes. The data provider anonymizes G_t and publishes its anonymized version $\bar{G}_t(\bar{V}_t, \bar{E}_t, \bar{R}_t)$, where \bar{V}_t, \bar{E}_t , and \bar{R}_t are the set of nodes, edges, and relationship types of \bar{G}_t .

We use k -ad [1] to protect the identity of any user u in \bar{G}_t . As \bar{G}_t contains both attributes' values and relationships of u , an adversary can exploit the background knowledge at time t about u , denoted $\mathcal{BK}_t(u)$, which contains all of the attributes' values and relationships at time t that the adversary knows about user u in real-life. In [1], it is proved that the adversary is not able to re-identify user u by using the background knowledge about u at time t (i.e., $\mathcal{BK}_t(u)$) and the attributes' values and out-/in-degrees extracted from \bar{G}_t (i.e., $I(\bar{G}_t, v)$) with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$. We illustrate the attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees that the adversary can extract from an anonymized KG in the following example.

Example 3. By using \bar{G}'_0 (Fig. 2a), adversaries can extract the following information about $user:2$ and $user:3$: their attributes' values $I_a(\bar{G}'_0, user:2) = I_a(\bar{G}'_0, user:3) = \{(age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}$, out-degree information $I_o(\bar{G}'_0, user:2) = I_o(\bar{G}'_0, user:3) = \{(follows, 0)\}$, and in-degree information $I_i(\bar{G}'_0, user:2) = I_i(\bar{G}'_0, user:3) = \{(follows, 1)\}$. Then, $I(\bar{G}'_0, user:2) = I(\bar{G}'_0, user:3) = \{(age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}, \{(follows, 1)\}$.

Unfortunately, if an adversary gains access not only to \bar{G}_t but also to the $w - 1$ previous anonymized KGs $\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \dots, \bar{G}_{t-1}$, he/she can potentially re-identify any user u appearing at least once in these KGs. We formally define these users as follows:

Definition 1 (Historical Users Set): Let $\bar{g}_t^w = (\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \bar{G}_{t-w+2}, \dots, \bar{G}_t)$ be a series of w continuous k -ad anonymized KGs that a data provider has published. The Historical Users Set of \bar{g}_t^w , denoted as $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$, is the set of users appearing at least once in these KGs. Formally:

$$\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w) = \bigcup_{t-w+1 \leq i \leq t} \bar{V}_i^U$$

Example 4. Let $\bar{g}_2^3 = (\bar{G}_0, \bar{G}_1, \bar{G}_2)$ be the series of anonymized KGs, shown in Fig. 3. The Historical Users Set of the series is: $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_2^3) = \{user:0, user:1, user:2, user:3, user:4, fake:0\}$.

An adversary can re-identify a user u in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ by combining the background knowledge that he/she knows about u from times $t - w + 1, t - w + 2, \dots, t$ and the series of u 's attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees that he/she can extract from anonymized KGs in \bar{g}_t^w . We formally define the adversary knowledge as follows:

Definition 2 (Adversary Knowledge): Let $\bar{g}_t^w = (\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \bar{G}_{t-w+2}, \dots, \bar{G}_t)$ be a series of w continuous k -ad anonymized KGs that a data provider has published. The knowledge that an adversary can use to re-identify a user $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ contains:

- The series of background knowledge that the adversary knows about user u : $\mathcal{BK}_t^w(u) = (\mathcal{BK}_{t-w+1}(u), \mathcal{BK}_{t-w+2}(u), \dots, \mathcal{BK}_t(u))$.
- The series of attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees that the adversary can extract from \bar{g}_t^w : $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = (I(\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, u), I(\bar{G}_{t-w+2}, u), \dots, I(\bar{G}_t, u))$.

Example 5. The adversary can extract the series of attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_2^3 (Fig. 2), \bar{g}_2^3 (Fig. 3) of $user:3$ as: $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:3) = ((\{(age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}, \{(follows, 1)\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{(age, 21), (age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}), \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:3) = ((\{(age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}, \{(follows, 1)\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{(age, 40), (age, 55), (job, Engineer)\}, \{(follows, 0)\}, \{(follows, 1)\}))$.

Based on the above knowledge, an adversary can re-identify his/her victim u by using an attacking mechanism \mathcal{T} to identify if a user $v \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ is the representation of u . We formally define the attacking mechanism as follows:

Definition 3 (Attacking Mechanism): Let $\bar{g}_t^w = (\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \bar{G}_{t-w+2}, \dots, \bar{G}_t)$ be a series of w continuous k -ad anonymized KGs that a data provider has published, $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ be the user that an adversary wants to re-identify, and v be an arbitrary user in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$. The attacking mechanism \mathcal{T} is represented as

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{BK}_t^w(u), \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u, v \text{ is the same user.} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We define the Privacy Disclosure Risk based on the attacking mechanism \mathcal{T} as follows:

Definition 4 (Privacy Disclosure Risk): Let $\bar{g}_t^w = (\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \bar{G}_{t-w+2}, \dots, \bar{G}_t)$ be a series of w continuous k -ad anonymized KGs that a data provider has published, and $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ be the user that an adversary want to re-identify. The Privacy Disclosure Risk of u is the confidence that the adversary can re-identify u by using his/her background knowledge and attacking mechanism \mathcal{T} :

$$risk(\mathcal{T}, \bar{g}_t^w, u) = \frac{1}{\sum_{v \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)} \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{BK}_t^w(u), \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v))}$$

Example 6. Let assume that an adversary has access to \bar{g}_2^3 (Fig. 2). As the series of $user:0$'s attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_2^3 : $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:0)$ is unique, the Privacy Disclosure Risk of Ken is $risk(\mathcal{T}, \bar{g}_2^3, Ken) = \frac{1}{1} = 1$. Similarly, the Privacy Disclosure Risk of all remaining users in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_2^3)$ is 1.

B. Protection Model

We present k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree (k^w -tad) to protect users from being re-identified with a confidence higher than $\frac{1}{k}$ even if an adversary combines attributes' values and out-/in-degrees of these users in w continuous anonymized KGs. Specifically, let \bar{g}_t^w be a series of w continuous k -ad

anonymized KGs. We ensure that, for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$, there are at least $k-1$ other users $v \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ whose series of attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_t^w (i.e., $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)$) is equal to that of u (i.e., $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)$). We formally define k^w -tad as follows:

Definition 5 (k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree): Let \bar{g}_t^w be a series of w continuous k -ad anonymized KGs that a data provider has published. \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree (k^w -ad), if and only if, for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$, there exists a subset of users in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$, denoted as $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)$, such that $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \{v \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w) | \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)\}$ and $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)| \geq k$.

Example 7. We have $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:0) = \mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:1) = \{user:0, user:1\}$, $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:2) = \mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:3) = \{user:2, user:3\}$, and $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, user:4) = \mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, fake:0) = \{user:4, fake:0\}$. As for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_2^3)$, $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_2^3, u)| \geq 2$, \bar{g}_2^3 satisfies 2^3 -tad.

If a series of KGs \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad, the Privacy Disclosure Risk of all users in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$ is at most $\frac{1}{k}$.

III. ALGORITHM

Our Cluster-based Time-Varying Knowledge Graph Anonymization Algorithm (CTKGA) aims at modifying the structure of the original KG such that users' identities in its anonymized version are protected according to k^w -tad. The algorithm relies on two global parameters, that is, k, w , which are set by data providers. More precisely, let $\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} = (\bar{G}_{t-w+1}, \dots, \bar{G}_{t-1})$ be the series of $w-1$ previous anonymized KGs, generated by CTKGA. Given a KG G_t at time t , CTKGA generates the anonymized version of G_t : \bar{G}_t according to two main steps: clusters generation and knowledge graph generalization.

The cluster generation step aims at generating a set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t containing users in G_t such that all of these clusters have at least k real/fake users and the series of attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} of users who are in the same cluster is identical. Moreover, for every deleted user, who is not in \mathcal{C}_t but was in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$, there are at least $k-1$ other deleted users that have the same series of attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} .

In the knowledge graph generalization step, we use the Knowledge Graph Generalization Algorithm (KGG) [1] to generate \bar{G}_t , the anonymized version of G_t , by adding and removing edges in G_t such that attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees of users in \bar{G}_t who are in the same cluster are identical.

A. Clusters Generation

All clustering algorithms relies on a notion of distance between users to group users into clusters such that closer users are grouped into the same cluster. As the distance between users, we make use of an information loss metric which measures information loss of making the attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees of two users identical. To be as general as possible, our algorithm allows data providers to use any information loss metric (i.e., ADM [1], ATDM [1]) to calculate the distance between pairs of users in their

Algorithm 1 Clusters Generation($G_t, \mathcal{D}_t, \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, \mathcal{A}, k, w$)

Input: G_t : the original KG at time t ; \mathcal{D}_t : the distance matrix of users in G_t ; \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} : the series of $w-1$ previous anonymized KGs; \mathcal{A} : the clustering algorithm; k, w : two positive numbers.

Output: The set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t .

```
1:  $\mathcal{U}^w \leftarrow V_t^U \cup \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ 
2:  $\mathcal{C}^w \leftarrow \{c \subseteq \mathcal{U}^w \mid \forall u, v \in c \wedge \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)\}$ 
3:  $\mathcal{C}_t \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4: for  $c \in \mathcal{C}^w$  do
5:    $\mathcal{U}_c \leftarrow c \cap V_t^U$ 
6:    $\mathcal{U}_d \leftarrow c \setminus V_t^U$ 
7:    $\mathcal{C}_c \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8:   if  $0 < |\mathcal{U}_d| < k$  then
9:     Remove  $k - |\mathcal{U}_d|$  users from  $\mathcal{U}_c$ .
10:  end if
11:  if  $|\mathcal{U}_c| \geq k$  then
12:     $\mathcal{C}_c \leftarrow$  run clustering algorithm  $\mathcal{A}$  with  $\mathcal{D}_t$  and  $\mathcal{U}_c$ 
13:     $\mathcal{C}_c \leftarrow \{c_v \in \mathcal{C}_c \mid |c_v| \geq k\}$ 
14:  else
15:    if  $c$  is the cluster of new users then
16:       $\mathcal{C}_c \leftarrow$  add  $k - |\mathcal{U}_c|$  fake users to  $\mathcal{U}_c$ .
17:    end if
18:  end if
19:   $\mathcal{C}_t \leftarrow \mathcal{C}_t \cup \mathcal{C}_c$ 
20: end for
21: return  $\mathcal{C}_t$ 
```

KGs. Then, we use a distance matrix \mathcal{D}_t to store the distance between pairs of users in V_t^U , which is given as a parameter to our cluster generation algorithm.

Algorithm 1 describes our clusters generation algorithm. The algorithm takes as input the original KG G_t at time t , two positive integers: k, w , the clustering algorithm \mathcal{A} , the distance matrix \mathcal{D}_t , and the series of $w-1$ previous anonymized KGs \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} . First, it generates the set of users who existed in both V_t^U and any of the $w-1$ previous anonymized KGs, denoted as \mathcal{U}^w (line 1). Next, it finds clusters of users in \mathcal{U}^w , denoted as \mathcal{C}^w , such that the series of attributes' values and out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} of those in the same clusters is identical (line 2). New users who are in V_t^U but were not in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ are in the same cluster since their attributes and relationships are not published yet. It then initializes the set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t with the empty set (line 3). Next, for each cluster c in \mathcal{C}^w , it finds the set of users who exist in both c and V_t^U , denoted as \mathcal{U}_c , (line 5), and the set of users in c who have been removed from G_t , denoted as \mathcal{U}_d (line 6). It then initializes the set of clusters \mathcal{C}_c with the empty set (line 7). If \mathcal{U}_d has less than k users, it randomly removes $k - |\mathcal{U}_d|$ users in \mathcal{U}_c (line 9). Otherwise, it uses the clustering algorithm \mathcal{A} to split users in \mathcal{U}_c into clusters and assign these clusters to \mathcal{C}_c (line 12). Then, it only keeps valid clusters which has at least k users in \mathcal{C}_c (line 13). If \mathcal{U}_c has less than k users and c is the group of new users, it adds $k - |\mathcal{U}_c|$ fake users to \mathcal{U}_c (line 16). Then, it generates a cluster containing these fake users and users in

\mathcal{U}_c and adds the cluster to \mathcal{C}_c . The generated clusters \mathcal{C}_c are then added to \mathcal{C}_t (line 19). Finally, our algorithm returns the set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t (line 21).

B. Privacy Analysis

Given a series of anonymized KGs \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfying k^{w-1} -tad, a KG G_t is generated by adding/removing edges and nodes of G_{t-1} , and the set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t generated by our algorithm, we want to prove that: (A) inserted users in G_t are in clusters that have at least k users (see Theorem 1); (B) deleted users are not in clusters in \mathcal{C}_t and for every deleted user, his/her series of attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees is indistinguishable from that of $k-1$ other deleted users (see Theorem 2); (C) updated users also are in clusters that have at least k users and all users in the same cluster have the same series of attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} (see Theorem 3). Re-inserted users in G_t , who have been previously deleted in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} , are in clusters that have at least k users since they are in both $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ and G_t (according to Theorem 3). If these users have been deleted in anonymized KGs that have been published earlier than those in \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} , they also are in clusters that have at least k users because they are in G_t but not in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ (according to Theorem 1). Finally, we prove that \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad in Theorem 4.

Theorem 1. Let G_t be the current version of the original KG and \mathcal{C}_t be the set of clusters returned from Algorithm 1, executed with two positive numbers: k, w . Let $\bar{V}_t^U = \cup_{c \in \mathcal{C}_t} c$ be the set of users in \mathcal{C}_t and $\mathcal{U}_t^i = \bar{V}_t^U \setminus \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ be the set of new and fake users of \mathcal{C}_t . For every user $u \in \mathcal{U}_t^i$, u is in a cluster in \mathcal{C}_t , denoted c_u , such that c_u has at least k users.
Proof. Let u be an arbitrary user in \mathcal{U}_t^i and c_u be u 's cluster in \mathcal{C}_t . Suppose c_u has less than k users. If \mathcal{U}_t^i has at least k users, c_u will have at least k real users (lines 13). Otherwise, c_u has at least k fake/real users (line 16). Therefore, c_u always has at least k users. But this contradicts to the fact that c_u has less than k users. Therefore, we can conclude that for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}_t^i$, u is in a cluster in \mathcal{C}_t , denoted c_u , such that c_u has at least k users. \square

Theorem 2. Let G_t be the current version of the original KG and \mathcal{C}_t be the set of clusters returned from Algorithm 1, executed with two positive numbers: k, w . Let $\bar{V}_t^d = \cup_{c \in \mathcal{C}_t} c$ be the set of users in \mathcal{C}_t and $\mathcal{U}_t^d = \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}) \setminus \bar{V}_t^d$ be the set of deleted users. If \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}_t^d$, there is a set $\mathcal{C}_t^d(u) = \{v \in \mathcal{U}_t^d \mid \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)\}$ such that $|\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)| \geq k$.

Proof. Suppose \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad and there is a user $u \in \mathcal{U}_t^d$ such that $|\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)| < k$. Let c_u be the cluster in \mathcal{C}^w and c_u contains u (line 2). As \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, c_u also has at least k users and $\forall v \in c_u, \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$. $\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)$ contains deleted users in c_u . Since Algorithm 1 removes users in c_u such that there are at least k deleted users (line 9), $|\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)| \geq k$. But this contradicts the fact that $|\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)| < k$. Therefore, if \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, for every user $u \in \mathcal{U}_t^d$, $|\mathcal{C}_t^d(u)| \geq k$. \square

Theorem 3. Let G_t be the current version of the original KG and \mathcal{C}_t be the set of clusters returned from Algorithm 1, executed with two positive numbers: k, w . Let $\bar{V}_t^U = \cup_{c \in \mathcal{C}_t} c$ be the set of users in \mathcal{C}_t and $\mathcal{U}_t^u = \bar{V}_t^U \cap \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$ be the set of users existing in both \bar{V}_t^U and $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1})$. If \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, for every user u in \mathcal{U}_t^u , u is in a cluster in \mathcal{C}_t , denoted c_u , such that c_u has at least k users and $\forall v \in c_u$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$.

Proof. Suppose \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad. Let u be an arbitrary user in \mathcal{U}_t^u and c_u be its cluster in \mathcal{C}_t . Suppose c_u has less than k users or there is a user $v \in c_u$ such that $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) \neq \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$. Let c be the cluster in \mathcal{C}^w and c contains u (line 2). As \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, c also has at least k users and $\forall v \in c$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$. If c has less than k real users, Algorithm 1 does not add it to \mathcal{C}_t (line 11). In this case, real users in c are protected with deleted users (according to Theorem 2). If c has at least k real users, Algorithm 1 generates c_u , where $c_u \subseteq c$ and u is in c_u (line 12-13). c_u has at least k users since it is in \mathcal{C}_c , which only contains clusters that have at least k users (line 13). Moreover, $\forall v \in c_u$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$ as c_u is a subset of c . But this contradicts the fact that c_u has less than k users or there is a user $v \in c_u$ such that $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) \neq \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$. Therefore, we can conclude that if \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, for every user u in \mathcal{U}_t^u , u is in a cluster in \mathcal{C}_t , denoted c_u , such that c_u has at least k users and $\forall v \in c_u$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$. \square

Theorem 4. Given a series of w continuous KGs \bar{g}_t^w , if all $\bar{G}_t \in \bar{g}_t^w$ are generated by our algorithm, \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad.

Proof. We prove this theorem by induction on t . At time $t = 0$, the set of clusters \mathcal{C}_t returned from Algorithm 1 consists of new users. Then, all clusters in \mathcal{C}_t have at least k users (according to Theorem 1). By using the Knowledge Graph Generalization Algorithm (KGG) [1] to generate the first anonymized KG \bar{G}_0 , we make the attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees of users in the same clusters identical. Then, for every user u in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_0^w)$, $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_0^w, u)| \geq k$. Therefore, at time $t = 0$, \bar{g}_0^w satisfies k^w -tad.

In the following paragraphs, we prove the induction step. Suppose \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad and \bar{g}_t^w does not satisfy k^w -tad. The set of users in \bar{G}_t , \bar{V}_t^U , consists of all of inserted/re-inserted/updated users. These users are in clusters in \mathcal{C}_t . Let c be an arbitrary cluster in \mathcal{C}_t and u be an arbitrary user in c . c has at least k users and $\forall v \in c$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)$ (according to Theorem 1, 2, and 3). As we use KGG to make attributes' values and relationships' out-/in-degrees of users in the same clusters identical in \bar{G}_t , $\forall v \in c$, $I(\bar{G}_t, u) = I(\bar{G}_t, v)$. Thus, $\forall v \in c$, $\mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)$. Since c has at least k users, there is a set $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \{v \in \bar{V}_t^U | \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)\}$ such that $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)| \geq k$. As u is arbitrary, for every user $u \in \bar{V}_t^U$, $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)| \geq k$.

Let $\mathcal{U}_t^d = \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} \setminus \bar{V}_t^U$ be the set of deleted users in \bar{G}_t . Let u be an arbitrary user in \mathcal{U}_t^d . According to Theorem 2, there is a set $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \{v \in \mathcal{U}_t^d | \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, v)\}$

and $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u)| \geq k$. Because users in $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u)$ are not in \bar{G}_t , for every user $v \in \mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1}, u)$, $I(\bar{G}_t, u) = I(\bar{G}_t, v)$. Then, the set $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \{v \in \mathcal{U}_t^d | \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)\}$ also has at least k users. As u is arbitrary, for every user u in \mathcal{U}_t^d , $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) \geq k$.

Because $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w) = \mathcal{U}_t^d \cup \bar{V}_t^U$, for every user u in $\mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w)$, there is a set $\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \{v \in \mathcal{U}(\bar{g}_t^w) | \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, u) = \mathcal{I}(\bar{g}_t^w, v)\}$ such that $|\mathcal{C}(\bar{g}_t^w, u)| \geq k$. Therefore, \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad. But this contradicts the fact that \bar{g}_t^w does not satisfy k^w -tad. Then, we can conclude that if \bar{g}_{t-1}^{w-1} satisfies k^{w-1} -tad, \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad.

Therefore, we can conclude that if all $\bar{G}_t \in \bar{g}_t^w$ generated by our algorithm, then \bar{g}_t^w satisfies k^w -tad. \square

IV. CONCLUSION

The previous anonymization solutions for KGs do not allow data providers to publish many anonymized versions of their KGs. We remedy this problem by presenting k^w -Time-Varying Attribute Degree (k^w -tad) which protects the identities of users appearing at least once in w continuous anonymized KGs. Moreover, we present the Cluster-based Time-Varying Knowledge Graph Anonymization Algorithm (CTKGA) to generate anonymized KGs satisfying k^w -tad. Then, we prove that the resulting anonymized KGs prevent adversaries from re-identifying users even though data providers update their original KG by inserting/re-inserting/deleting their users or updating edges of their users. Our work is the starting point of anonymization solutions for KGs and it can be extended to overcome limitations of k -anonymity model, by considering, for instance l -diversity [2] or differential privacy approaches.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from CONCORDIA, the Cybersecurity Competence Network supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 830927.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.-T. Hoang, B. Carminati, and E. Ferrari, "Cluster-based anonymization of knowledge graphs," in *18th International Conference on Applied Cryptography and Network Security*, 2020.
- [2] S. Ji, P. Mittal *et al.*, "Graph data anonymization, de-anonymization attacks, and de-anonymizability quantification: A survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, pp. 1305–1326, 2017.
- [3] C.-H. Tai, P.-J. Tseng *et al.*, "Identity protection in sequential releases of dynamic networks," *IEEE transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 635–651, 2013.
- [4] K. Macwan and S. Patel, "Privacy preserving approach in dynamic social network data publishing," in *International Conference on Information Security Practice and Experience*. Springer, 2019, pp. 381–398.
- [5] X. Zhang, J. Liu *et al.*, "Large-scale dynamic social network directed graph k-in&out-degree anonymity algorithm for protecting community structure," *IEEE Access*, pp. 108 371–108 383, 2019.
- [6] A.-T. Hoang, B. Carminati, and E. Ferrari, "Cluster-based anonymization of directed graphs," in *Proceedings of the 5th IEEE International Conference on Collaboration and Internet Computing*, 2019, pp. 91–100.